

IMPACT OF SPARSE PROFILE SAMPLING ON THE RECONSTRUCTION OF SUB-SURFACE OCEAN TEMPERATURE FROM SURFACE INFORMATION

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Abstract—Projection of the dense surface measurement to subsurface using background information is a key approach in mapping the 3D ocean temperature. In the last years, a new inverse method combining self-organizing map (SOM) and hidden Markov model (HMM), PROFHMM, has been proposed for retrieving sub-surface ocean variables from the surface measurements. So far, this method requires a training dataset providing complete time-series of sets of surface and subsurface data. However, in reality, the spatiotemporal resolution of sub-surface data is sparser than the surface one and some subsurface profiles can be missing in a given training dataset.

In this study, we extend PROFHMM to handle the sparsity in the subsurface vertical profile time-series and introduce a method to evaluate its robustness with respect to the proportion of profile available at an instant t . In our specific experiments where temperature profiles are reconstructed from sea surface temperature and shortwave radiation data at 5 days interval, we found that the method works as long as this proportion is higher than 70%.

I. MOTIVATION

Three dimensional (3D) mapping of ocean temperature is a challenging task due to the nature of sampling strategies in the current global ocean observing systems. Sea surface temperature (SST) measurement from space provides the richest information regarding spatial and temporal resolutions but its access is limited to the surface information. Autonomous floats networks represented by Argo program [1] are sampling subsurface

profiles in global scale, but its target spatiotemporal coverage is sparse compared to the SST measurement. Projection of the dense surface measurement to subsurface using background information is a key approach in mapping the 3D ocean temperature. Recently, the new projection method based on the combination of a self-organizing map (SOM) and a hidden Markov model (HMM), PROFHMM, for retrieving sub-surface ocean variables from the surface measurement is proposed [2].

In this study, we have examined the robustness of PROFHMM under the case of temporally sparse subsurface sampling.

II. METHOD

A. Self-Organizing Map (SOM)

A self-organizing map (SOM) is an artificial neural network (ANN) that performs dimensionality reduction and clustering of a given set of training data [3]. SOM can be considered as undirected graphs whose vertices are neurons (or classes) which are associated to a referent vector (or weights). A class is represented by an index defining its position within the SOM and a referent vector is a vector of the same size as the data we want to classify. The set of classes are representative of a whole cluster of these data.

In PROFHMM [2], a set of two SOMs have been trained: one denoted M_{obs} for the surface data and one denoted M_{dis} for the subsurface.

In our experiments we have:

- Surface SOM M_{obs} containing $N_{\text{obs}} = 2 \times 70 = 140$ classes. Referent vectors of dimension 2 represent the sea-surface temperature and the incoming shortwave radiation.
- Vertical profile SOM M_{dis} containing $N_{\text{dis}} = 4 \times 70 = 280$ classes. Referent vectors of dimension 26 represent the temperature at 26 different levels of depth from $0m$ to $92m$ with a higher vertical resolution near the surface.

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Note that the purpose of this study is not to find the optimal PROFHMM configuration for this problem, but to extend the method to the case with missing data and to present a method to evaluate its robustness. For the same dataset, a better configuration could be found and provide better results.

The topologies of both M_{obs} and M_{dis} are rectangular maps. The coordinates of a particular class of one of these maps, denoted c^t ($t \in \mathbb{N}$, arbitrary here), is given by a couple of integers (x_t, y_t) . The distance $D(c^1, c^2)$ between 2 classes c^1 and c^2 is the Euclidean distance

$$D(c^1, c^2) = \sqrt{(x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2}. \quad (1)$$

As an ANN, there are two phases in the SOM construction process: a training phase and a mapping phase. The training phase builds the map. For each training iteration, all the referent vectors are updated as following [3]:

- 1) Finds the Best Matching Unit (BMU): class whose referent vector is the closest to the input (in the input data space)
- 2) Update every referent vector:
 - a) compute the distance between the class associated with the referent vector and the BMU (in the map)
 - b) update the referent vector so that the closer their associated class is to the BMU (in the map) the more their referent vector will be modified towards the input data.

After training, the mapping phase classifies a new input vector into the class associated with the nearest referent vector.

One of the main advantages of applying a SOM to oceanographic data, which are conditioned and constrained by physical laws is that referent vectors associated to topologically neighbouring classes will have similar physical properties and behaviours (e.g. they represent the same period of the year).

B. Hidden Markov Model (HMM)

Hidden Markov Model (HMM) is a Markov model in which the system has unobservable (hidden) states. In simpler Markov models, the state is always visible and depends solely on the previous state. In an HMM, the current observable state depends only on the current hidden state (emission) and the current hidden state depends only on the previous hidden state (transition). The parameters of a HMM are the probabilities of every

emission and transition, they are stored in 3 matrices: Tr, Em and π :

$$\text{Tr}(i, j) = p(c_{\text{dis}}^t = j | c_{\text{dis}}^{t-1} = i) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i, j \in [1..N_{\text{dis}}] \\ c_{\text{dis}}^t, c_{\text{dis}}^{t-1} \in M_{\text{dis}} \end{array} \right. ,$$

$$\text{Em}(i, j) = P(c_{\text{obs}}^t = j | c_{\text{dis}}^t = i) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i \in [1..N_{\text{dis}}] \\ j \in [1..N_{\text{obs}}] \\ c_{\text{dis}}^t \in M_{\text{dis}} \\ c_{\text{obs}}^t \in M_{\text{obs}} \end{array} \right. ,$$

$$\pi(i) = p(c_{\text{dis}}^0 = i) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} i \in [1..N_{\text{dis}}] \\ c_{\text{dis}}^0 \in M_{\text{dis}} \end{array} \right. ,$$

called transition matrix, emission matrix and the initial probabilities, respectively [4] [5] [6].

These matrices are initialized by counting transitions and emissions that occurred in the training dataset [7]. The elements of the matrices are then optimized using the Baum-Welch algorithm (B-W) [5].

From the setting of SOMs in our experiments, we have

- 140 classes of M_{obs} : 140 referent surface data (observable states),
- 280 classes of M_{dis} : 280 referent vertical profiles (hidden states).

III. CONTRIBUTION

A. Initializing Em and Tr

Extension of PROFHMM to the sparse sub-surface training dataset is achieved by implementing a new counting strategy in initializing Em and Tr with sparse time-series as follows:

- An emission at instant t is counted only if the vertical profile at this instant t is not missing
- A transition at instant t is counted only if both the vertical profile at instants t and $t - 1$ are not missing

Thus if one profile (instant t) is missing we lose 2 transitions ($t - 1 \rightarrow t$ and $t \rightarrow t + 1$) and 1 emission (instant t).

Our choice of the counting strategy for sparse time series is the simplest way we could imagine, but other methods of counting emission and transition could be implemented and compared in future work. For instance provided a good enough time resolution, a transition between a state at instant t and $t + 2$ could be counted with some weight if $t + 1$ state is missing.

Note also that not only surface data which are associated with a non-missing vertical profile, but all the surface observations can be used in the B-W algorithm.

B. Radius of neighborhood function

In practice, there is not enough training data to estimate properly the elements of E_m and Tr (and especially Tr) even with a complete set of surface and subsurface time-series. To overcome this problem, Charantonis (2015) [2] suggested using a neighbouring function that exploits the topological properties of the SOM. We used a similar yet slightly different neighbourhood function to propagate the probability of a class to its neighbour. We first calculate Tr^{b-w} and Em^{b-w} as described previously, using the counting procedure and the B-W algorithm (the subscript $b-w$ stands for “B-W algorithm”), then we improve the values by calculating Tr^s and Em^s (the subscript s stands for “smooth”) using the following expressions:

$$Tr^s(i, j) = S_{Tr}^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{dis}} \exp\left(-\frac{D(j, k)}{\sigma}\right) Tr^{b-w}(i, k) \quad (2)$$

$$Em^s(i, j) = S_{Em}^{-1} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{dis}} \exp\left(-\frac{D(j, k)}{\sigma}\right) Em^{b-w}(i, k) \quad (3)$$

Where $D(j, k)$, see Eq. (1), is the distance between the class j and k within M_{dis} , σ is the so-called radius of the neighborhood function and S_{Tr} , S_{Em} are normalizing factor such as $\sum_{j=1}^{N_{dis}} Tr^s(i, j) = \sum_{j=1}^{N_{dis}} Em^s(i, j) = 1$. σ is a regularizing term: if σ is small, the smooth quantities will be very close to the original B-W computation, if σ is large, Tr^s and Em^s will not vary much throughout the map. In our case, σ is computed according to the actual transitions that occurred while training M_{dis} . Therefore, σ represents the typical distance of a transition in the training time-series. This typical distance is strongly linked to the nature of the data used and the shape of the SOM, thus using the same radius as [2] used could have been irrelevant. Instead, we defined a criterion that could be used for any other application and configuration of PROFHMM.

C. Penalize long distance transitions

In the case of complete times-series, counting and smoothing in initializing Em and Tr give good enough results and B-W does not have a great impact on the accuracy of the estimates. However, since B-W is an expectation-maximization algorithm, it only needs as input the observation time-series. Then the fewer vertical profiles we had compared to surface data during the initialization the greater the impacts of B-W and

observable time-series are. This might cause some discontinuity in the vertical profile reconstructed. To prevent this problem we used another neighbourhood function that decreases the probability to transit from i to j if they are far from each other in M_{dis} . Once again we used the same radius of σ in this neighbourhood function.

$$Tr^l(i, j) = S^{-1} \exp\left(-\frac{D(i, j)}{\sigma}\right) Tr^s(i, j)$$

where the subscript l stands for “local” and S is a normalizing factor such as $\sum_{j=1}^{N_{dis}} Tr^s(i, j) = 1$.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Experiments setup

Time series of temperature profile data are produced by one-dimensional numerical ocean model GOTM configured with atmospheric forcing at the Bermuda Atlantic Time-series Study (BATS) site [8]. Starting from the initial state in 1990, the model was integrated up to 2007. The model states and the surface atmospheric forcing are saved every 12 hours. The training and testing sets are then generated by temporally averaging hidden state: temperature profile and observable states: sea surface temperature (SST) and downward shortwave radiation (DWSR) within 5 days window. The temperature profile is further averaged in the vertical axis over 5 model levels. Removing the first two years record as model spinning-up period, we define training and testing datasets as follows:

- Training dataset: 1992-2003: total length of time-series: 879
- Testing dataset: 2004-2007: total length of time-series: 292

The choice of DWSR as an observable state in addition to SST is made based on the dynamical understanding that DWSR is a key forcing driver that introduces seasonal asymmetry in the sub-surface temperature profile in Spring and Autumn.

To emulate missing profiles we used a Bernoulli distribution of parameter p at each instant t . To have a first overview of the behaviour of the method applied with missing data, we drew 10 subsets of the complete data set for each p decreasing from 1 (no missing data) to 0.50 with 0.05 steps. According to the results we then focused on $0.65 < p \leq 1$, drawing this time 50 subset for each p .

The same SOM M_{obs} and M_{dis} were used for mapping all the vertical profiles and they were trained

with a complete time-series. In the ideal case, a new SOM should have been trained for each sample and each probability. This would have been extremely time-consuming and would not have had a great impact on the results since the SOM needs fewer vertical profiles to give satisfying results and it is not the main cause of the error in the final reconstruction. However, different values of Tr and Em are estimated for each p and each subset.

The quality of the profile reconstruction on the testing dataset is evaluated using the root-mean-square error (RMSE) with respect to each depth as a metric. Another metric could have been selected if the study called for it (such as the maximum error in time for example).

The results are compared to a lower-bound which is the climatology (the average profile of each given date over the years 1992-2003). Nevertheless, note that this lower-bound is computed using the complete dataset without missing data, and by consequence should be considered as a reference value for the performance of the algorithm.

B. Results and interpretation

Fig. 1. Boxplot comparison of performance of PROFHMM for different values of p (probability of missing a vertical profile).

For values of p down to 0.7, the reconstructions obtained are close to the reconstruction obtained with $p = 1$, as seen in Fig. 1. The RMSE observed remain consistently bellow those obtainable if simply using a climatology.

In Fig. 2, it can be seen that, the performance is a lot better for the first 40 meters of depth, which is where the results matter the most in this problem (See Figure 2).

Finally, the method outperforms the climatological reconstruction as long as the probability of getting a

Fig. 2. RMSE with respect to depth on the testing data set.

vertical profile is higher than 0.70 (See Figure 1). This is highly encouraging, especially given that the configuration of PROFHMM has not been optimized and that further improvement could be done for initializing the matrices Em and Tr . It suggests that, for this particular problem of temperature reconstruction, PROFHMM could be applied in a realistic in-situ dataset with missing profiles such as Argo floats measurements. Further investigations remain to be done to generalize these results to other problem (e.g. chlorophyll-a profiles) or other time and spatial scales.

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